

Kinetics of irradiated semiconductor catalyzed degradation of picric acid

J. D. Joshi^{a*}, Jabali Vora^b, Sangita Sharma^b and Chirag C. Patel^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar-388 120, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, North Gujarat University, Patan-384 265, India

Manuscript received 1 April 2002, revised 1 October 2002, accepted 18 December 2002

The chemical degradation of picric acid by irradiation in presence of semiconducting ZnO was studied. Kinetics of the reaction were found to be affected by parameters like concentration of substrate, pH, amount of photocatalyst, light intensity etc. The effects of radical quencher and sensitizer were also studied. A probable mechanism is suggested.

Photo-oxidation of organic compounds on semiconductor (SC) catalysts has been extensively studied¹ but only a few examples of direct oxygenation of organic compounds on SC catalysts are available². Photocatalytic reactions in presence of ZnO suspensions have been studied³. Some photochemical redox reactions at the zinc oxide-water inter-phase in additive free systems have been investigated⁴. The literature survey reveals that the kinetics of photodegradation of picric acid in presence of SC have not been carried out. Picric acid is explosive at higher temperatures (> 300°) and also explosive by percussion. Due to the dangerous properties of picric acid, it was chosen for the study to check the possibility of decomposition.

Results and discussion

The study of kinetics of photocatalytic degradation of picric acid was carried out at 0.05 mM concentration, with 200 mg semiconductor, 5.68 mW cm⁻² light intensity, 4.0 pH, 295 K temperature and at λ_{max} 410 nm. A linear least-squares graph⁵ of $2 + \log O. D.$ vs exposure time was drawn and its slope determined. The first order rate coefficients have been obtained for all kinetic runs of this photocatalytic reaction by using expression, $k = 2.303 \times \text{slope}$. The photocatalytic degradation of picric acid was found to be a two-step reaction – in the first step optical density slowly decreased without red- or blue-shift, and in the second step, the rate of degradation reaction increased to around three times its first step value for the typical run. Values of k_1 and k_2 found were 1.91×10^{-3} and $5.76 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$, respectively. Rate of reaction is dependent on various constituents taking part in the reaction.

The impact of concentration of picric acid upon the rate of the degradation was observed. As the concentration of

the substrate was increased, the rate of both the steps decreased expectedly.

pH variation had two types of effects on the degradation of picric acid. When pH was increased from 3 to 10, the value of k_1 steadily increased, however, the value of k_2 decreased (Table 1). It may be possible that the first step is more affected by radicals like $\cdot\text{OH}$ but the second step seems less sensitive to the same.

Table 1. Effect of pH

Zinc oxide = 200 mg, [C₆H₃N₃O₇] = 0.05 mM, light intensity = 5.68 mW cm⁻², temp. = 295 K, λ_{max} = 410 nm

pH	$10^3 k_1$ min ⁻¹	$10^3 k_2$ min ⁻¹
3	1.84	6.29
4	1.91	5.76
5	2.23	5.53
6	2.37	5.46
7	2.53	5.07
8	2.83	4.58
9	2.92	4.21
10	3.22	4.19

The effect of variation in the amount of photocatalyst was also observed. The rate of photocatalytic degradation of picric acid increased with increase in the amount of photocatalyst upto a certain amount (200 mg). It may be considered like a saturation point above which an increase in the amount of semiconductor has no appreciable effect on the rate of photocatalytic degradation of picric acid.

To study the effect of light intensity on the photocatalytic degradation of picric acid, the distance between the light source and exposed surface of the semiconductor was varied (Table 2). The results indicate that photocatalytic reaction is enhanced as the intensity of light in-

creases. This increase is due to the fact that more photons will be available for excitation at semiconductor surface on increasing the light intensity and in turn, more electron hole pairs will be generated, thus resulting into enhanced rate of photocatalytic degradation; both k_1 and k_2 show increase with increase in light intensity.

Table 2. Effect of light intensity

Zinc oxide = 200 mg, pH = 4.0, $[C_6H_3N_3O_7] = 0.05$ mM, temp. = 295 K, $\lambda_{max} = 410$ nm

Light intensity mW cm ⁻²	$10^3 k_1$ min ⁻¹	$10^3 k_2$ min ⁻¹
3.05	0.92	4.54
4.47	1.46	4.84
5.68	1.91	5.76
8.79	2.53	6.22
11.07	2.83	8.64

As alcohols are usually effective in quenching free radicals, methanol, ethanol and isopropanol were selected for this study. It was observed that in case of all the three alcohols, both the reaction rates were found to decrease, that means quenching of the reaction was observed. Furthermore, ethanol had a better quenching tendency and this was also observed here. In case of isopropanol due to solvent effect, λ_{max} value of the solution had a 5 nm red-shift. In this way, the possible participation of free radicals during the course of reaction is ascertained. The results are reported in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of radical quencher

Quencher	λ_{max}	$10^3 k_1$ min ⁻¹	$10^3 k_2$ min ⁻¹
Methanol	410	1.30	2.65
Ethanol	410	1.04	1.32
Isopropanol	415	1.54	1.57

Normally dyes are capable of sensitizing photocatalytic reaction. In the present study, however, it was observed that crystal violet, methylene blue and methyl orange all at 10 ppm concentration were not able to enhance the reaction rate but decreased both the rates.

Mechanism : In organic molecule, irradiation of light promotes an electron from a filled (HOMO) to unfilled (LUMO) molecular orbitals. Analogous to organic molecule in SC, the filled (valence band VB) and empty (conduction band CB) molecular orbitals are separated by band gap energy. Electromagnetic radiation of energy equal to or greater than band gap energy is required to promote an electron from VB to CB, creating electron deficiency or hole in VB. The electron promoted to CB are mobile. ZnO is a widely used SC photocatalyst in many organic reactions

due to non-toxic nature chemical stability, availability and capability of repeated use without substantial loss of catalytic activity. The energy of irradiation of ZnO by low energy UV-radiation ($\lambda > 387$ nm) results in the formation of electron hole pair ($e-h^+$),

The electron promoted from VB to CB is readily available for transfer and the positive equivalent, the hole in VB is ready to accept the electron from the substrate.

The charge carriers can recombine or trapped by a defect site or electron transfer with adsorbed electron donors and acceptors :

It is reported that several species, radicals and radical ions like $\bullet OH$, H^+ , $\bullet O_2$, H_2O_2 , $\bullet HO_2$, O_2 etc. are present especially in aqueous medium⁶. Some of these species play important role in the reduction and oxidation reactions occurring in the reaction medium. As the experiments were carried out in the presence of air which contained oxygen, the electron promoted to CB in ZnO reacted with oxygen to form superoxide radical ion ($O_2^{\bullet -}$), which oxidized the organic molecule.

It was observed that the products of photocatalytic degradation of picric acid in presence of ZnO were colorless gases with virtually no solid residue left in the solution. Hence, a probable reaction is proposed as under :

By the same analogy, $\bullet OH$ can also be shown to carry out redox reactions :

Experimental

Zinc oxide (Merck) was used and others were of A.R. grade. Picric acid is usually mixed with around 10-20% water to prevent accidental hazards during transportation. The moist solid was carefully dried and its prepared solution was standardized by pH-metric titration, then appropriate dilutions were made. A 0.05 mM stock solution (10 ml) of picric acid and semiconductor (zinc oxide powder, 60 mesh; 200 mg) were mixed. The solution was exposed to 500 W halogen lamp from the top side. Then the optical density was measured at 410 nm using a spectrophotometer (Systronics 106) in a glass cuvette with path-length 1.0 cm and the progress of photocatalytic reaction was observed.

References

1. H. Al-Ekabi in "Photochemistry in Organized and Constrained Media", ed. V. Ramamurthy, VCH Publication, Weinheim, 1991, p. 495.
2. M. A. Fox and M. T. Dulay, *Chem. Rev.*, 1993, **93**, 341; P. V. Kamat, *Chem. Rev.*, 1993, **93**, 267; N. N. Rao and P. Natarajan, *Curr. Sci.*, 1994, **66**, 742.
3. A. Sharma, B. Sharina, R. P. Mathur and S. C. Ameta, *Pollution Res.*, 2001, **20**, 419.
4. R. Ramaraj and J. R. Premkumar, *Curr. Sci.*, 2000, **79**, 884; L. C. Chen and T. C. Chou., *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1993, **85**, 201; C. Srinivasan, *Curr. Sci.*, 1997, **76**, 534; J. D. Joshi, J. J. Vora, S. S. Dharma and C. C. Patel, *Bull. Pure Appl. Sci.*, 2001, **20c**, 33; J. D. Joshi, J. J. Vora, S. S. Sharma, C. C. Patel and A. B. Patel, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2002, **14**, 761.
5. G. D. Christian, "Analytical Chemistry", Wiley, 4th ed., New York, 1986; J. E. Freund and R. E. Walpole, "Mathematical Statistics", Prentice Hall of India, 4th ed., New Delhi, 1987.
6. V. Maurino, C. Minero, E. Pelizzetti, P. Piccinini, N. Serpone and H. Hidaka, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. (A)*, 1997, **109**, 171.